

AYURVEDA CONCEPT OF MEDOROGA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO OBESITY

Vd. Bhushan Prakash Kawle*

Associate Professor Kayachikitsa Sardar Patel Ayurvedic College Dongariya Balaghat.

*Corresponding Author: Vd. Bhushan Prakash Kawle

Associate Professor Kayachikitsa Sardar Patel Ayurvedic College Dongariya Balaghat.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17275077>

Article Received on 20/08/2025

Article Revised on 10/09/2025

Article Accepted on 30/09/2025

INTRODUCTION

Medoroga- Santarpanajanya Vyadhi “Santarpana” means to nourish and satisfy the body. Also, “Brimhana” is a synonym of Santarpana which is also responsible for the nourishment of body. The causative factors of “Santarpanajanya vyadhi” are:

सन्तर्पयत यः तिग्धैर्पधुरैरुपरुतर्तछिलैः। नवान्नैः नपवर्दयैश्च र्वां सैश्चानूर्वाररजैः। र्ोरसैर्ौतिकैश्चान्नैः
रैतिकैश्चातर्त्राशः। चेिाद्वेषी दिवास्वप्नशय्यासनसुखे रतः। रोर्ास्तस्योर्जायन्ते सन्तर्पणतनतर्तजाः।

Aharaja Nidana- The food which is Snigdha, Madhur, Guru, Navanna, Navamadya, Gaudika, Anup Mamsa, Matsaya Mamsa, milk and its preparations, etc. Viharaja Nidana- Asya-sukha, shayya-sukha, Chesta-dwesh, Divaswapana, Abhyanga, Snaan, Avyayam and Achintana, etc. Specific causes (Nidaan) of Sthoulya Vyadhi are described in Charak Samhita which are as follows

तिततस्थौल्यैर्तसम्र्णाद्रुधुरशीततिग्धोर्योर्ािव्यायार्ािव्यवायादिवास्वप्नाद्धषपतनत्यत्वाि-
तचन्तनाद्बीजस्वभावाच्चोर्जायते।^[4]

In Ayurvedic text it also mentioned that Sthoulya is very bad for health. For this they elaborate the reason behind that

अततस्थूलस्य तावियुषो हासो जवोर्ोधः कृच्छरव्यवायता
िोर्पल्यां िोर्पल्यां स्वेिर्ाधः क्षुिततर्त्रां
र्ासाततयोर्श्चतत भवन्त्यौ िोषाः।^[4]

Atisthula and Atikrisha are always affected by some complaints.^[2] Acharya Charaka has quoted Sthoulya as being under the eight varieties of reprehensible persons, such as Astauninditiya Purusha.^[3] In this modern era and fast-moving life, many drastic changes have occurred in dietary habits, modes of lifestyle, and various regimens of lifestyle. The majority of individuals are habituated to a sophisticated and comfortable lifestyle. This results in paving the way for many metabolic disorders. These are popularly referred to as lifestyle disorders, and obesity is one of them. In Ayurveda, Obesity is described as ‘Medoroga’ or ‘Sthoulya Roga’. Continuous indulgence in fatty food, fried items, etc., along with a sedentary lifestyle, leads to excess body fat accumulation deposited in the numerous body channels. According to the ICMR-INDIAB study prevalence rate of obesity and central obesity varies from 11.8% to 31.3% and 16.9% - 36.3% respectively. In India, abdominal obesity is one of the major risk factors for cardiovascular disease (CVD).^[4] Obesity is such a disease that provides a

platform for so many complications like HTN, DM, OA, infertility, as well as psychological disturbances like stress and depression. Appropriate Ayurvedic internal medicines along with Shodhana procedures are used to achieve the best results, without any side effects. Vamana, Virechan, Basti, and Udvartan, according to the vitiation of Doshas, these Shodhana procedures give effective results. Pathya - Apathya (Diet management) & Lifestyle modifications play an important role in the management of Sthoulya. This article is an attempt to explore the Nidana (etiology), Samprati (pathogenesis), Rupa (symptoms), and Chikista Sutra (treatment) of Sthoulya with its Pathya-Apathya.

Nidana: Nidana is the factor that causes the disease process. In our classics, Nidana has been given utmost importance because the knowledge of Nidana is essential to understand the Samprati, to know the Saadyasadhyata, and to plan for Chikitsa, as the first step of treatment starts with Nidana Parivarjana.

Purvarupa: None of the Ayurvedic texts has described the Purvarupa of Sthoulya. Acharya Charaka, in Nidana Sthana, mentioned a similar pathogenesis of Prameha and Medoroga because there is vitiation of Kapha and Meda in both of them. Therefore, the Purvarupa of Prameha^[10] and Medovaha Strotodushti Lakshanas^[11] can be considered the Purvarupa of Sthoulya.

- *Atinidra*
- *Tandra*
- *Alasya*
- *Visra Sharira Gandha*
- *Anga Gaurava*
- *Anga Shaithilya*
- *Ati Sweda*

Rupa: The *Rupa* manifests in the fifth stage (*Vyaktavastha*) of *Vyadhi Kriya Kala*. Acharyas broadly assert the symptomatology of *Sthoulya*.

Charaka Samhita mentions the cardinal symptoms of *Sthoulya* as

Pratyatma Lakshana: *Medomamsa Ativruddhi, Chala Sphik, Chala Udara, Chala Stana, Ayathaopachaya, Anutsaha*.

Pratyatma Lakshana: *Medomamsa Ativruddhi, Chala Sphik, Chala Udara, Chala Stana, Ayathaopachaya, Anutsaha*.^[12]

Besides the *Lakshanas*, eight detrimental effects of *Sthoulya* have also been explained by Acharya *Charaka* as

Ashta Mahadosha^[13]

1. *Ayushohrasa* (Diminution of lifespan)
2. *Javoparodha* (Lack of interest in Physical activity)
3. *Kricchra Vyavaya* (Difficulty in having coitus)
4. *Dourbalya* (Debility)
5. *Dourgandhya* (Unpleasant smell from the body)
6. *Swedaabadha* (Excessive sweating)
7. *Kshudhatimatra* (Excessive hunger)
8. *Pipasatiyoga* (Excessive thirst)

Bheda: *Vagbhata* has explained three types of *Sthoulya* for better management^[14]

1. *Hina Sthoulya*
2. *Madyama Sthoulya*
3. *Adhika Sthouly*

Samprapti: According to *Charaka*, due to *Avarana* (obstruction) in the *Strotas* (channels) by the *Meda*, there is *Vridhhi* of *Koshtasthit Samana Vayu*, which in turn causes *Ati Sandhukshana* of *Jatharagni*. The increase in *Jatharagni* leads to rapid digestion of consumed food and leaves the person craving more food. If at all due to some reason, the person doesn't receive more food, the increased *Agni* causes *Dhatu Pachana*, which may lead to various complications. But because of hunger, people tend to eat more, and the cycle continues. In this way, it becomes a vicious circle, creating excessive, improperly formed *Medo Dhatu*, giving rise to various symptoms. Because of such a condition of *Strotorodha*, the other *Dhatus* are not nourished properly, causing *Shaithilya* (flabbiness) of *Dhatus* before *Meda Dhatu* and depletion of *Dhatus* next to *Medo Dhatu*.^[15]

According to *Sushruta*, *Kaphavardhaka Ahara, Adhyasana, Avyayama, Diwaswapna*, etc., lead to the formation of an *Ama Rasa*, i.e., *Apachit Adya Rasa Dhatu*. The *Madhura Bhavayukta Ama Rasa* moves within the body, and the *Snigdhamsha* of this *Ama Rasa* causes *Srotosanga*, which leads to *Sthoulya*.^[16]

Samprapti: According to *Charaka*, due to *Avarana* (obstruction) in the *Strotas* (channels) by the *Meda*, there is *Vridhhi* of *Koshtasthit Samana Vayu*, which in turn causes *Ati Sandhukshana* of *Jatharagni*. The increase in *Jatharagni* leads to rapid digestion of consumed food and leaves the person craving for more food. If at all, due to some reason, the person.

Chikitsa: The general principle of treatment in *Ayurveda* is

1. *Nidana Parivarjana*
2. *Samshodhana*
3. *Samshamana*

While describing the *Chikitsa* of *Sthoulya*, Acharya has said that it is very difficult to treat an *Atisthoola* person because, if *Karshana* therapy is applied, then it leads to further aggravation of already aggravated *Jathra Agni* and *Vayu*, and if *Brimhana* therapy is applied, it further increases the *Meda*. The management of *Sthoulya* is explained in detail as follows:

Guru Cha Atarpanam Cheshtam Sthulanam Karshanam Prati

- *Guru Ahara and Atarpana Chikitsa are the line of treatment for Sthoulya*
- *Bahya Shodhana - Ruksha Udvartana*^[18]

Abhyantara Shodhana

- *Snehana - Medohara Taila like - Sarshapa Taila, Tugaraka Taila*
- *Swedana - Mrudu Swedana^l, Niragni Sweda like Guru Pravarana, Bahupana, Kshudha Nigraha, Atap Sevan, Vyayama.*
- *Pancha Karma - Vaman^l, Vireacana, Nasya, Ushna-Teekshna Basti^[25], Lekhana Basti, Raktamokshana*

Ayurvedic Management

In *Ayurvedic* texts, *Nidana Privarjana* is the first line of choice for managing any disease. According to *Ayurveda*, *Aaharj* and *Viharaj* *Nidaan* are the main culprits in *Sthoulya Vyadhi*. So, first of all, correcting improper *Aahar* and *Vihar* is the most important management of *Sthoulya* (*Medoroga*) apart from *Aushadha* only.

Therefore, there are three lines of choices for management/ treatment for *Medoroga*:

- Management through *Aahar*
- Management through *Vihar*
- Management through *Aoushadha*

Use of Deepana

Pachana Modalities Manda Medodhatvagni is the principal cause of Medoroga, which develops at the level of Dhatvagni. Agni works on the metabolism of fat. The Deepana drugs increase the weak metabolic process, and the Pachana drugs help in the digestion of Ama, which is an intermediate metabolic toxin. The sticky property of Ama may block the channels of the body, which may lead to improper nutrient supply to the organs or even the cells, which in turn create disease. Most of the Deepana Pachana modalities work on the virtue of Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Rasa; Ushna Virya; Katu Vipaka, and sometimes Prabhav. All these properties help in destroying the excess Kapha, Ama, and Meda, which are accumulated in body cells because of the blockage of body channels. Pathaya Aahar प रशातिका तप्रयङ्गुश्च श्यामाका यवका यवाः। जूराहाः। कोद्रवा मुदाः। कुलत्थाश्चक्रमुद्काः। आढकीनां च बीजातन पटोलामलकः। सहभोजनार्थं प्रयोज्यातन पानां चानु मधूदकम्। अरिष्ठांश्चानुपानार्थं मेदोमांसकफापहान्। अतिरुथौल्यतवनाशाय सांतवभज्य प्रयोजयेत्।^[5] Yava, Godhum, Takra, Madhu, Jo, Moong, Aamlaki, Sava, Kanguni Dhanya, Kodo, Kulthi, Arhar seeds, Parwal, Medmamsanashak Arista etc.

3. DISCUSSION

In Ayurveda treatment, Siddhanta is based on the Viparit Guna. As Sthoulya is a Santarpanajanya Vyadhi, so we can cure Medoroga or Sthoulya by Viparit Guna Chikitsa, i.e., Aptarpan. That's why we need to follow Aptarpan Siddhanta in every type of treatment, including Aahar, Vihaar, Auoshadha, and Panchkarma. Lifestyle is also a major factor causing Sthoulya. So, it becomes necessary to improve lifestyle in every manner to cure this. According to Ayurveda, we treat the disease at the level of Dhatus, and at this level, Dhatwagni is responsible for further nourishment of the next Dhātu. Dhatwagni Mandya is the main culprit behind all the diseases. Like in Sthoulya Medodhatuagni, Mandya is the reason. So, we need to correct the Medodhatuagni. By this, we can treat Sthoulya. Including all these things, one more unique concept of Ayurveda is that two persons are not exactly alike, also they don't react alike. So Ahaar, Vihar, and Auoshadha mentioned in Ayurveda are not the same for every individual because of the variation of Prakriti, Desh, Kaal, and Agni of an obese person. In other words, there is need of more personalized approach is necessary when treating obesity.

REFERENCE

1. Gallagher EJ, Karnieli E, LeRoith D. The metabolic syndrome: From insulin resistance to obesity and diabetes. *Med Clin North Am.*, 2011; 95: 855.
2. Austin MA, Hokanson JE, Edwards KL. Hypertriglyceridemia as a cardiovascular risk factor. *Am J Cardiol.*, 1998; 81: 7B–12.

3. KruthHS. Lipoprotein Cholesterol and Atherosclerosis. *Curr Mol Med.*, 2001; 1: 633–53.
4. Castelli W. Lipoproteins and cardiovascular disease: Biological basis and epidemiological studies, *Value Health*, 1998; 1: 105 9.
5. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala. In: Charaka Samhita, Sutra Sthana, Ashtauninditeeya Adhyaya, 21/3. 5th ed. Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2009; 116.
6. Chakrapani D. In: Commentator, Sushruta Samhita, Sutra Sthana, Doshadhatumalakshayavruddhi Vijnaniya Adhyaya, 15/4. 8th ed. Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Choukhambha Orientalia, 2005; 68.
7. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala. In: Charaka samhita, Sutra Sthana, Deerghanjeeviteeya Adhyaya, 1/61. 5th ed. Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2009; 17.
8. Sushruta. In: Sushruta Samhita, Sutra Sthana, Doshadhatumalakshayavruddhi Vijnaniya Adhyaya, 15/4. 8th. Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Choukhambha Orientalia, 2005; 67.
9. Agnivesha, Charaka, Dridhabala. In: Charaka samhita, Sutra Sthana, Ashtaninditeeya Adhyaya, 21/4. 5th ed. Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2009; 116.
10. Sushruta. In: Sushruta Samhita, Sutra Sthana, Dravyasangrahaneeeyam Adhyaya, 38. 8th ed. Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Choukhambha Orientalia, 2005; 164–8.
11. Vagbhata. Ashtanga Samgraha, Sutra Sthana, Vividhadravayaganasangraha Adhyaya, 16, translated by Srikantha Murthy, 9th ed. Varanasi: Choukhambha Orientalia, 2005; 310.
12. Vagbhata. In: Ashtanga Hrudaya, Sutra Sthana, Shodhanadiganasangraha Adhyaya, 15. 9th ed. Anna Moreshwar Kunte, Krishnashastri Navare, Harishastri, editors. Varanasi: Choukhambha Orientalia, 2005; 229.
13. Sharma PV, editor. Dhanvantari Nighantu 4th ed. Varanasi: Choukhambha Orientalia, 2005.